

Supplemental Materials

Taylor, S., and J. Waite-Cusic. 2026. Evaluation of bioprotective potential of *Bacillus* spp. cell-free supernatant (CFS) against *Listeria* spp. in cultured ingredient for application to cottage cheese. Journal of Dairy Science. Supplemental Materials DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17941554

Supplementary Table S1. Strain information for *Bacillus* producer strains and *Listeria* target strains used in Taylor et al., 2025.

Supplementary Table S2. Experimental sample layout for 96-well plate assay and data management for test plates (1-5), including the sample preparation type (cell-free supernatant: CFS; foamed cell-free supernatant: CFS-F; foamed, freeze-dried cell-free supernatant: CFS-F-FD), biological replicates (producer and target), initial cell density (log CFU/mL) of target strains.

Supplementary Table S3. *Bacillus* strains with submitted GRAS Notifications, including those which have successfully navigated FDA's GRAS Notification Process (n = 17) along with a single strain that is awaiting FDA review (pending status) as well as GRAS submissions that were withdrawn by the notifier (n = 5).

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Supplementary Figure S2. Processing and analysis of optical density data to calculate the change in lag phase duration (Δ LPD) to quantify antilisterial activity of *Bacillus* cell-free supernatant (CFS).

Supplementary Figure S3. Inhibitory effects of foamed cell-free supernatant (CFS-F; top) and foamed, freeze-dried cell free supernatant (CFS-F-FD; bottom) of *Bacillus* spp. on the growth of *Listeria* target strains.

Supplementary Figure S4. Photographs of representative cottage cheese formulations inoculated with *Listeria monocytogenes* WRLP96 after 15 d of storage at 7°C.

Supplementary Table S1. Strain information for *Bacillus* producer strains and *Listeria* target strains used in Taylor et al., 2025.

Bacterial species	Strain designation	SRR number (raw reads)	SRA number (assembly)	Assembled Contigs	Genome Size (bp)	Isolation source (original strain source)	Reference
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	HD49A	SRR32592070 SRR32592071	SAMN47215667	2	3,608,039	Sample type: Concentrated skim milk Provided by: Joy Waite-Cusic, Oregon State University (Corvallis, OR) Location: Utah; Isolated: 07/08/2020	
	VF0409D	SRR32592075 SRR32592074	SAMN47215669	6	3,598,486	Sample type: Raw cream Provided by: Joy Waite-Cusic, Oregon State University (Corvallis, OR) Location: Utah; Isolated: 04/09/2021	
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Y487	SRR32592076 SRR32592084	SAMN47215668	1	4,084,366	Sample type: Kombucha Provided by: Chris Curtin, Oregon State University (Corvallis, OR)	
<i>Listeria innocua</i>	WRLP438	SRR35111234 SRR35111233	N/A	N/A	N/A	Sample type: Environmental sample from produce facility. Location: Oregon; Isolated: 04/2019 Provided by: Jovana Kovacevic, Oregon State University (Portland, OR)	Jorgensen et al., 2020
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	WRLP42	SRR25437801	N/A	N/A	N/A	Sample type: Tomme d'or cheese Location: British Columbia, Canada Provided by: Jovana Kovacevic, Oregon State University (Portland, OR)	Brown et al., 2024
	WRLP96	SRR25437743	N/A	N/A	N/A	Sample type: Environmental sample from dairy processing facility Location: British Columbia, Canada Provided by: Jovana Kovacevic, Oregon State University (Portland, OR)	Brown et al., 2024

N/A indicates that genomic assemblies were not uploaded to NCBI database.

Brown, S.R.B., Bland, R., McIntyre, L., Shyng, S., Weisberg, A.J., Riutta, E.R., Chang, J.H., and Kovacevic, J. 2024. Genomic characterization of *Listeria monocytogenes* recovered from dairy facilities in British Columbia, Canada from 2007 to 2017. Doi:10.3389/fmicb.2024.1304734

Jorgensen, J., Waite-Cusic, J. and Kovacevic, J. 2020. Prevalence of *Listeria* spp. in produce handling and processing facilities in the Pacific Northwest. Food Microbiology 90: 103468. Doi:10.1016/j.fm.2020.103468

Supplementary Table S2. Experimental sample layout for 96-well plate assay and data management for test plates (1-5), including the sample preparation type (cell-free supernatant: CFS; foamed cell-free supernatant: CFS-F; foamed, freeze-dried cell-free supernatant: CFS-F-FD), biological replicates (producer and target), initial cell density (log CFU/mL) of target strains. All producers were cultured in food-grade TSBYE analog (FG-TSBYE).

Experiment Description	96-well Plate	Producer strains evaluated	Purification Methods	Producer Culturing Replicates (Biological)	Target Replicates (Biological)	Target strain(s) evaluated	Initial target cell density (Log CFU/mL)	Wells Cropped (Erratic early)	Wells Eliminated (Erratic throughout)
Dose dependency	1	<i>B. subtilis</i> Y487 <i>B. pumilus</i> VF0409D <i>B. pumilus</i> HD49A	CFS-F-FD	R1, R2	1, 2, 3, 4	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP42	6.48	16/84	8/84
Dose dependency	2	<i>B. subtilis</i> Y487 <i>B. pumilus</i> VF0409D <i>B. pumilus</i> HD49A	CFS-F-FD	R1, R2	1, 2, 3, 4	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP96	6.36	26/80	2/80
Dose dependency	3	<i>B. subtilis</i> Y487 <i>B. pumilus</i> VF0409D <i>B. pumilus</i> HD49A	CFS-F-FD	R1, R2	1, 2, 3, 4	<i>L. innocua</i> WRLP438	6.21	23/80	0/80
Evaluating antilisterial activity of CFS-F	4	<i>B. subtilis</i> Y487 <i>B. pumilus</i> VF0409D <i>B. pumilus</i> HD49A	CFS-F	R1	1, 2, 3, 4	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP42 <i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP96 <i>L. innocua</i> WRLP438	5.84 5.85 5.72	17/96	1/96
Evaluating antilisterial activity of CFS	5	<i>B. subtilis</i> Y487 <i>B. pumilus</i> VF0409D <i>B. pumilus</i> HD49A	CFS	R1	1, 2, 3, 4	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP42 <i>L. monocytogenes</i> WRLP96 <i>L. innocua</i> WRLP438	6.31 6.24 6.26	0/84	2/84

Supplementary Table S3. *Bacillus* strains with submitted GRAS Notifications, including those which have successfully navigated FDA's GRAS Notification Process (n = 17) along with a single strain that is awaiting FDA review (pending status) as well as GRAS submissions that were withdrawn by the notifier (n = 5). All GRAS applications were submitted using scientific basis as the support for the safety determination. Full GRAS notification inventory available at: <https://hfppappexternal.fda.gov/scripts/fdcc/index.cfm?set=GRASNotices> (Accessed November, 26, 2025).

Species	Strain	GRAS Notice No.	FDA Response Date	Format	Intended Use	Maximum use level
<i>Bacillus coagulans</i>	IS-2	526/1177	2015/2024	Spore preparation	Food ingredient/ Infant formula	9.3 log CFU/serving /8.3 log CFU/100 mL
	GBI-30	399/660	2012/2017	Spore preparation	Food ingredient/ Infant formula	9.3 log CFU/serving/8.3 log CFU/100 mL
	MTCC 5856	601	2016	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
	M2017813	1243	2025	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
	SANK 70258	691	2017	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
	SNZ1969	597/864	2016/2020	Spore preparation	Food ingredient /Infant formula	9.3 log CFU/serving /8.3 log CFU/100 mL
	DSM 17654	949	2021	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
	PTA-127366	1263	Pending	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	None	559	Withdrawn (2015)	Spore preparation	Banana wash water	3 ppm
	None	560	Withdrawn (2015)	Spore preparation	Banana wash water	3 ppm
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	None	561	Withdrawn (2015)	Spore preparation	Banana wash water	3 ppm
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	ATCC BS50 PTA-127287	1131	2023	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving
	Bss-19	969	2021	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	10 log CFU/serving
	DE111	831	2019	Spore preparation*	Food ingredient (including infant formula)	10 log CFU/serving (8.3 log CFU/100 mL)
	NRRL 68053	1143	2024	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	10 log CFU/serving
	NRRL 68054	1218	2025	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	10 log CFU/serving
	SG188	905	2020	Spore preparation	Ingredient for beverages and dry, shelf-stable foods	9 log spores/serving
	ATCC AAN000002	1095	2023	Spore preparation	Tracer for FDA- regulated commodities	6 log spores/g
	BS-MB40 PTA 122264	955	2021	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	10 log CFU/serving
	ATCC SD- 7280	956	2021	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.8 log spores/serving
	R0179	1007	Withdrawn (2022)	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9 log CFU/serving
	None	562	Withdrawn (2015)	Spore preparation	Banana wash water	3 ppm in wash water
<i>B. velezensis</i>	PTA-127359 (BV 379)	1231	2025	Spore preparation	Food ingredient	9.3 log CFU/serving

*Method of manufacture does not describe procedures or conditions that would ensure sporulation or separation of cells or spores from the culturing media; however, shelf-stability descriptions suggest that this is intended to be spore preparation.

Supplementary Figure S1. Photographs of 96-well transfer stamps on tryptic soy agar with 0.6% yeast extract (TSAYE) following incubation at 37°C for 24 h and the 96-well plate used to evaluate dose dependency of producer CFS-F against *Listeria monocytogenes* WRLP96 presented as an example interpretation of checking for contamination or confirming inhibitory activity. A) Transfer and stamp of 96-well test plate (C) after adding CFS to the 96-well plate and adding positive *L. monocytogenes* inoculum to the control wells to the 96-well plate. No contamination from *Bacillus* spores or *Listeria* cross-contamination in test wells are observed. B) Transfer and stamp 96-well test plate (C) prior to incubation to confirm inoculation with the target *Listeria* strain with the exception of the negative control wells (G1-G4; purple). C) Test 96-well plate after incubation at 37°C for 24 h in the FilterMax spectrophotometer to visually confirm turbidity and lack of pellicle formation from producer contamination. D) Transfer and stamp of 96-well test plate (C) following incubation 37°C for 24 h in the FilterMax spectrophotometer.

Negative control wells (G1-G4) were not inoculated which was confirmed by no bacterial colony formation on plates A, B, and D. No increase in optical density was observed at the end of the incubation period (Plate C).

Positive control wells (G5-G8) were inoculated with target *Listeria* strain which was confirmed plate A, B and D based on typical colony morphology. Visible increase in optical density was observed at the end of the incubation period (Plate C).

No visible optical density increase at the end of the incubation period indicating complete inhibition of target strain by the *Bacillus*-CFS. Transfer stamps for the same well positions confirm the inoculation of the test well (Plate B) and survival of *Listeria* throughout the incubation period (Plate D) indicating bacteriostatic activity of the *Bacillus*-CFS.

No visible optical density increase at the end of the incubation period complete inhibition of target strain by the *Bacillus*-CFS. Transfer stamps for the same well positions confirm the inoculation of the test well (Plate B) and no detectable *Listeria* at the end incubation period (Plate D) indicating bactericidal activity of the *Bacillus*-CFS.

Supplementary Figure S2. Processing and analysis of optical density data to calculate the change in lag phase duration (Δ LPD) to quantify antilisterial activity of *Bacillus* cell-free supernatant (CFS). A) Normalized growth curve outputs (green) from the spectrophotometer were cropped at a maximum optical density of $OD_{595nm} = 0.20$. B) The growth curves were then modelled using the Mechanistic Growth Model (JMP 18.0) using the nonlinear fit curve function with a custom inverse prediction ($OD = 0.02$ or 0.07) to determine lag phase duration (LPD). The average LPD of the positive *Listeria* control LPD (blue line) was subtracted from the LPD of each growth curve (green line) to determine the inhibitory effect of the *Bacillus*-CFS on *Listeria* growth (Δ LPD). C) Each data point represents a calculated Δ LPD for an individual growth curve with a box-and-whisker plot displaying the distribution and variability of the Δ LPD of a given *Bacillus* CFS toward a specific *Listeria* target strain. The dashed black line at 0 h represents no inhibitory activity. The dashed line at 18 h represents complete inhibition (i.e., no *Listeria* growth within 24 h).

Supplementary Figure S3. Inhibitory effects of foamed cell-free supernatant (CFS-F; top) and foamed, freeze-dried cell free supernatant (CFS-F-FD; bottom) of *Bacillus* spp. on the growth of *Listeria* target strains. Each data point represented by a P1-P4 dot is the lag phase duration (LPD) of a *Listeria* spp. cultured in the presence of the CFS inversely predicted at an OD = 0.07 subtracted by the average of the lag phase duration (LPD) of a *Listeria* spp. cultured without CFS (positive control; n = 4). Growth curve modeling was performed using the Mechanistic Growth Model on JMP Pro 18.0.0.

Supplementary Figure S4. Photographs of representative cottage cheese formulations inoculated with *Listeria monocytogenes* WRLP96 after 15 d of storage at 7°C. A) Control cottage cheese formulation without the addition of *Bacillus* foamed, freeze-dried cell-free supernatant (CFS-F-FD). B) Cottage cheese formulation with the addition of *B. pumilus* VF0409D CFS-F-FD. Discoloration is due to the color of the CFS-F-FD. Cottage cheese formulations containing the CFS-F-FD displayed signs of curd swelling, discoloration and softening curds compared to the control.

A) Control cottage cheese formulation (dressing with no added CFS-F-FD)

B) Cottage cheese formulation with *B. pumilus* VF0409D CFS-F-FD

